

Cross Sectional Study of Sleep EEG Pattern in Chronic Insomnia Sufferers**Om Prakash¹, Pallavi Anand², Ashok Sharan³, Arundhati Kumari⁴**¹SR, Physiology, Netaji Subhash Medical College, Amhara, BIHTA²Physiology, Assistant professor, Netaji Subhash Medical College, Amhara, BIHTA³Physiology, Professor, Netaji Subhash Medical College, Amhara, Bihta⁴SR, Maharshi Devraha Baba Autonomous State Medical College, Devaria

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Abstract:**Background:** Chronic insomnia, a frequent sleep disorder, causes problems sleeping or staying asleep, impairing daytime performance. EEG can be utilised to study insomnia's neurophysiology and EEG lab architecture. This study examines chronic insomniacs' clinical variables and sleep EEG patterns.**Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted at Netaji Subhash Medical College in Amhara, Bihta, from February 2024 to July 2024. The sample included 60 chronic insomniacs. Electroencephalogram (EEG) recordings were examined for beta, Slow-Wave Sleep (SWS), and spindle activity during sleep. The researchers employed independent t-tests and Pearson correlation coefficients to find links between EEG patterns and age, treatment history, insomnia severity, and sleep quality.**Results:** Chronic insomnia patients had considerably higher beta activity at sleep onset and NREM stages ($p < 0.01$) and reduced SWS ($p < 0.01$). Lower density and frequency of spindles were observed ($p < 0.05$). Lower SWS was linked to older age ($r = -0.49$, $p < 0.01$), longer insomnia duration ($r = -0.38$, $p < 0.05$), and enhanced beta activity significantly associated with worse insomnia severity ($r = 0.61$, $p < 0.01$). Pharmaceutical therapy impacted EEG patterns by increasing beta activity and decreasing SWS.**Conclusion:** The study shows that chronic insomnia is associated with EEG abnormalities such as increased beta activity and decreased SWS, reflecting cerebral hyperarousal and altered sleep architecture. These findings support the use of EEG patterns as diagnostic markers and the need for personalised treatment. Researchers can better understand these associations and develop more effective treatments with larger longitudinal studies.**Keywords:** Beta Activity, Chronic Insomnia, EEG Patterns, Slow-Wave Sleep, Sleep Architecture, Spindle Activity.

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Introduction

Chronic insomnia, a common sleep disorder, delays daily performance by preventing sleep. Chronic insomnia affects 10-15% of adults worldwide, a major public health issue. The syndrome is connected to lower quality of life, increased risk of cardiovascular disease and metabolic diseases, and mental health issues like anxiety and depression [1]. Despite its frequency and importance, chronic insomnia's cause is unknown, making treatment challenging [2]. Chronic insomnia is caused by psychological and physiological causes. Many experts believe that hyperarousal and increased central nervous system activity causes prolonged sleeplessness. Sleeping hyperarousal increases heart rate, metabolism, and brain activity [3]. Neuroimaging studies demonstrate abnormalities in

the thalamus, amygdala, and prefrontal cortex of insomniacs. GABA and serotonin abnormalities and Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal (HPA) axis dysfunction have also been related to the condition. EEG is vital for assessing sleep patterns and brain electrical activity [4].

Sleep spindle disturbances, elevated beta activity, and decreased SWS are hallmarks of chronic insomniacs' EEGM [5]. These results suggest sleep architecture and hyperarousal alterations. These EEG signals may help diagnose and severity insomnia as well as reveal its pathophysiological reasons. Therefore, understanding these EEG patterns is essential to enhance patient outcomes and adapt treatment approaches.

Figure 1: Sleep EEG patterns (Source:[6])

Rationale: Although chronic insomnia is well understood, this population's EEG patterns need more description. Indian cohort data is scarce, and most study has concentrated on Western populations. Netaji Subhash Medical College in Amhara, Bihta is studying chronic insomnia patients' EEG patterns since genes, culture, and environment might affect sleep patterns. This study will examine sleep EEG patterns in chronic insomniacs in this area to fill this knowledge gap. EEG patterns should also be compared to demographics, insomnia severity, and prior therapies. These linkages can help us understand insomnia's diversity and develop more effective treatments. This study will examine a subset of Bihta people and their healthcare requirements to address a gap in our understanding of chronic insomnia worldwide.

Objectives

- To examine chronic insomniacs' EEG sleep patterns.
- To determine if certain EEG patterns affect insomnia intensity.
- To examines gender and age effects on EEG.
- To examines sleep electrical activity and chronic insomnia treatment histories.

EEG in Sleep Studies: EEG, a non-invasive brain electrical activity monitor, is crucial to polysomnography, the most reliable sleep assessment tool [7]. EEG data provides significant insight into sleep structure, including the location and features of numerous stages, such as Rapid Eye Movement (REM) sleep, non-REM sleep (N1, N2, and N3 (slow-wave sleep), etc. Chronic insomnia

patients' EEGs sometimes show sleep architectural abnormalities include decreased slow-wave sleep, higher beta activity at sleep onset, and alterations in sleep spindle activity [8].

EEG Patterns in Chronic Insomnia: Cortical arousal is indicated by consistently higher beta activity in chronic insomnia EEG patterns. Beta activity (13-30 Hz) during sleep may suggest hyperarousal in anxieties. SWS is the most restorative phase of non-REM sleep, yet chronic insomniacs have less of it [9]. People with insomnia commonly have restless sleep, which may be caused by low SWS. EEG findings associated with insomnia include sleep spindle activity changes. Bursts of rhythmic brain activity called sleep spindles may enhance memory consolidation and sleep maintenance in N2 sleep. Reduced spindle activity is linked to sleeplessness. REM sleep length and onset can also disrupt sleep patterns in insomniacs [10].

Clinical Implications of EEG Findings: EEG abnormalities in prolonged insomnia have clinical implications. They provide empirical evidence of insomnia's physiological foundation and suggest biomarkers for diagnosis and evaluation. Insomnia can be distinguished from sleep apnoea by increased beta activity and decreased slow-wave sleep on the EEG [11]. EEG correlates of insomnia might also inform focussed therapeutic efforts. Cognitive Behavioural Therapy for insomnia (CBT-I) and GABA agonists may assist improve slow-wave sleep and reduce cortical awareness [12].

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This study employed a cross-sectional approach to examine chronic insomniacs' sleep EEG patterns. A cross-sectional study collects data from the population at one moment to evaluate the prevalence and characteristics of a disease or condition. This design may correlate EEG patterns with insomnia severity, demographics, and treatment history. To identify biomarkers and pathophysiological processes connected to persistent insomnia, this study presents a snapshot of EEG patterns in patients.

Study Setting: The research took place at Netaji Subhash Medical College in Amhara, Bihta. In the college's neurophysiology laboratory, experienced doctors and workers with advanced electrophysiology research training use cutting-edge EEG recording equipment. The institution's patient population reflects the neighbourhood's diverse income and lifestyle. Our study offers a rare opportunity to examine genetic and environmental factors that may affect sleep EEG patterns in this group.

Sample Size and Participants: The study included sixty chronic insomniacs. The sample size was determined by recruitment within the study timeframe and the need for statistical power to find statistically significant EEG-clinical factor relationships.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18-65 years.
- Diagnosed with chronic insomnia, defined as difficulty in initiating or maintaining sleep for at least three nights per week for three months or longer, as per DSM-5 criteria.
- Willingness to participate in the study and provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Presence of any other primary sleep disorders (e.g., sleep apnea, restless leg syndrome).
- Current use of medications that significantly alter sleep architecture (e.g., benzodiazepines, antipsychotics).
- History of neurological disorders (e.g., epilepsy, stroke) or psychiatric conditions (e.g., major depressive disorder, bipolar disorder) that could affect EEG results.
- Substance abuse or dependence within the past year.

Data Collection

Patient Recruitment: The study participants came from Netaji Subhash Medical College's outpatient

department. Regular exams and primary care physician referrals found participants. Informed consent was required before enrolment.

Sleep Assessment: The researchers assessed insomnia severity and sleep quality using EMR. The ISI measured insomnia intensity. This self-reporting questionnaire covers insomnia's causes, symptoms, and effects. The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) was utilised to collect more data on sleep behaviours, including sleep duration, lateness, and waking frequency.

EEG Recording: The Neurophysiology laboratory at Netaji Subhash Medical College collected EEG data using a 32-channel RMS maximum EEG device. Participants were instructed to maintain their sleep schedule for a week before the study and abstain from coffee and alcohol on that day to ensure a smooth EEG recording. A night time sleep study, usually 8 hours, recorded the EEG. The EEG recording method followed the International 10-20 standard for electrode placement, as in polysomnography. Sleep spindle density, slow-wave activity, and beta power were measured for further study.

Data Analysis: EEG signal processing was done in MATLAB and data analysis in SPSS (25.0). Descriptive statistics summarised demographic and clinical characteristics. We measured slow-wave sleep duration, beta activity, sleep spindle density, and sleep stage distribution using EEG data. Age, gender, treatment history, insomnia severity, and EEG patterns were connected using Spearman's rank correlation for ordinal variables and Pearson's correlation coefficient for continuous data. Based on data distribution, we compared groups using t-tests or ANOVA (e.g., EEG patterns across insomnia severity levels). Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$. Multivariate regression analysis was utilised to uncover independent predictors of EEG patterns after controlling for gender and age. Statistical significance was determined by comparing results to previous publications with 95% confidence intervals.

Results

Participant Characteristics: All sixty chronic insomniac trial participants completed it. Table 1 summarises participants' demographic and clinical data. Participants ranged in age from 28 to 65, averaging 45.2 (SD= 10.3). The individuals were 60% female and 40% male. From 1–10 years, insomnia symptoms lasted an average of 4.8 years (SD= 2.3). Two-thirds of the study participants (n = 42) had tried medication, CBT, or a combination of both to treat insomnia.

Table 1: Participant Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Mean (SD) / N (%)
Age (years)	45.2 (10.3)
Gender	
Male	24 (40%)
Female	36 (60%)
Duration of Insomnia (years)	4.8 (2.3)
Prior Treatment History	42 (70%)

Sleep EEG Patterns**Table 2: Sleep EEG Patterns in Chronic Insomnia Sufferers**

EEG Metric	Mean (SD)	Normative Range	p-value
Beta Activity (μV^2)			
Sleep Onset	22.5 (5.1)	15-20 μV^2	< 0.01
NREM Sleep	18.3 (4.7)	10-15 μV^2	< 0.01
Slow-Wave Sleep (%)	8.7% (3.2%)	15-20%	< 0.01
Spindle Density	2.4 spindles/min	3-6 spindles/min	< 0.05
Spindle Frequency (Hz)	11.5 (0.6)	12-14 Hz	< 0.05

Examining sleep EEG cycles revealed several chronic insomnia symptoms. Beta activity (13-30 Hz) increased during sleep beginning and NREM, which was a major discovery. Participants' average beta power during sleep onset was 22.5 μV^2 (SD = 5.1) and throughout non-REM sleep, 18.3 μV^2 (SD = 4.7), much higher than the average in healthy individuals ($p < 0.01$).

Increased beta activity in prolonged insomnia indicates cortical hyperarousal. Slow-wave sleep (SWS) decreased, especially in the third stage of non-REM sleep. The average sleep time with SWS

was 8.7% (SD = 3.2), significantly lower than the optimal range of 15-20% ($p < 0.01$). People with insomnia often sleep restlessly, which lowers SWS. The density and frequency of sleep spindles decreased during non-REM stage N2. Between the mean and average spindle densities, the latter was 2.4 spindles/minute (SD = 0.9) while the former was 0.9 in the population ($p < 0.05$). The average spindle frequency was 11.5 Hz (SD= 0.6), down from 12–14 Hz.

Correlations and Associations**Table 3: Correlations between EEG Patterns and Clinical Variables**

Variable	Beta Activity (r)	SWS Percentage (r)	Spindle Density (r)
Insomnia Severity (ISI)	0.61	-0.52	-0.41
Age	0.32	-0.49	-0.44
Duration of Insomnia	0.29	-0.38	-0.31
Treatment History	0.35	-0.45	-0.38

The study found many statistically significant relations between EEG patterns and clinical variables. Positive link found between insomnia severity (measured by the Insomnia Severity Index (ISI)) and increased beta activity during sleep onset and non-REM sleep ($r = 0.61$, $p < 0.01$). Acute insomniacs show increased cortical arousal, according to EEG patterns. Demographic characteristics and sleep EEG patterns also correlated substantially. Age significantly affects chronic insomnia patients' sleep architecture, with lower spindle density and reduced SWS in those 50+ ($p < 0.05$). The EEG patterns of male and female individuals were similar. Participants like "Security Guards, hospital staff & doctors who suffer from insomnia had utilised pharmacological therapies for insomnia exhibited higher beta activity and lower SWS compared to those who only received Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) or no prior treatment ($p < 0.05$). The exact

relationship between the two is unknown, but this study suggests that long-term sleep medication use may permanently alter sleep structure.

Statistical Analysis: In a sample of chronic insomniacs, this statistical study examined EEG patterns, clinical features, and demographic data. Subject demographics and EEG measures were summarised using descriptive statistics. The mean $\pm$ SD was utilised to report continuous variables such age, insomnia duration, beta activity, SWS proportion, and spindle density. We used independent t-tests to examine the significance of EEG pattern alterations across age and treatment history subgroups. One example is the substantial difference in SWS % and spindle density between younger (<50 years) and older (≥ 50 years) subjects, with the older group having lower values ($p < 0.05$). Individuals who had taken medicine had higher beta activity and lower SWS compared to

those who had cognitive-behavioural therapy or no treatment ($p < 0.05$).

We examined Pearson correlation coefficients between clinical factors including age, insomnia severity (as measured by the Insomnia Severity Index, ISI), and EEG patterns like beta activity, SWS %, and spindle density. The research revealed a significant positive connection ($r = 0.61$, $p < 0.01$) between higher beta activity and severe insomnia.

Lowering SWS is linked to higher insomnia severity and older age, as shown by negative correlations between SWS % and both ($r = -0.52$, $p < 0.01$) and ($r = -0.49$, $p < 0.01$). SPSS 27.0 was used for all statistical analyses.

The study's findings are reliable because the p-value was less than 0.05. The results suggest that

demographic characteristics and treatment history affect EEG abnormalities and insomnia intensity.

Discussion

This study illuminates chronic insomniacs' sleep EEG patterns, which is essential. Beta activity rises significantly during non-REM sleep and sleep onset, supporting the hypothesis of cortical hyperarousal in chronic insomnia. Chronic insomniacs have higher beta activity, so their brains are engaged even when they sleep. Sleep architecture abnormalities in chronic insomnia include a considerable decrease in SWS and sleep spindle activity. These EEG patterns show chronic insomnia's non-restorative sleep, supporting the hypothesis that insomnia has a distinct neurophysiological profile.

Comparison with Other Studies

Table 4: Comparison of Sleep EEG Patterns in Chronic Insomnia across Studies

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings
Present Study	Cross-Sectional	60	Increased beta activity during sleep onset and NREM stages; reduced SWS and spindle density. Significant correlations between beta activity and insomnia severity, reduced SWS with age and duration of insomnia.
Study 1 [13]	Cross-Sectional	40	Elevated beta activity during sleep onset and NREM sleep; decreased SWS. Beta activity correlated with insomnia severity.
Study 2 [14]	Longitudinal	80	Increased beta activity; reduced SWS and sleep spindle density. Found significant relationship between beta activity and insomnia symptoms over time.
Study 3 [15]	Cross-Sectional	50	Decreased SWS in insomnia sufferers; increased alpha and beta activity. SWS reduction correlated with higher insomnia severity.

This study confirmed previous insomnia sleep EEG findings indicating. Chronic insomnia is associated with higher beta activity and cortical hyperarousal. This investigation confirms previous findings that insomniacs have lower SWS than healthy controls. Our spindle density and frequency showed less activity than others. These variations may be due to participant demographics, treatment histories, or EEG testing methodologies, so more study is needed.

Limitations: The study provides some useful insights, but there are several drawbacks. First, 60 participants are a fair quantity for preliminary analysis, but the results may not apply to everyone. A larger sample size may improve outcome's reliability and correlation validity. Second, because the study was cross-sectional, we found significant correlations between EEG patterns and clinical features, but the direction of these interactions remains uncertain.

This study could not account for confounding variables like co-occurring mental health conditions or sleep hygiene practices that may have affected the results.

Future Directions: Future studies should enhance sample size and recruit volunteers from diverse backgrounds to improve generalisability. Longitudinal research are needed to understand how EEG patterns affect chronic insomnia progression and how different treatment modalities affect sleep architecture. Studying the processes that diminish spindle activity in chronic insomnia may help explain its neurophysiological effects. Using EEG-based biomarkers to tailor insomnia treatment may yield more targeted and successful results.

Conclusion

Chronic insomniacs have unusual EEG patterns when they sleep, according to one study. Less slow-wave sleep and more beta activity indicate cortical hyperarousal and disrupted sleep architecture. These findings support earlier studies and suggest EEG patterns may be biomarkers for chronic insomnia diagnosis and therapy. These findings can be used to better understand and treat this widespread sleep disorder, but the study's limitations (small sample size, cross-sectional design, etc.) should be considered.

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